

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

EUROPEAN PERSPECTIVE OF GEORGIA. ECONOMIC REVIEW

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Abstract

The paper discusses the European perspective of Georgia, an economic overview. International indicators such as the Heritage Foundation's 2022 Index of Economic Freedom are analyzed; "Doing Business 2020" index of favorable conditions for doing business of the World Bank and the International Finance Corporation. Data on Georgia's integration with Western countries are given. A kind of parallel between Georgia and Moldova is drawn. The importance of Georgia's transport corridor between Europe and Asia is also mentioned. It is justified that Georgia is ahead of Moldova in important economic parameters. At the same time, Moldova is still a member of the CIS. Georgia officially left the CIS on August 18, 2009. And if only Ukraine and Moldova are granted candidate status, it would be an injustice to Georgia, to the Georgian society, which is so persistently trying to get closer to the European Union.

Keywords: European perspective, Economic achievements.

Introduction

The population of Georgia went through the most difficult period in the 90s: the war in Abkhazia, where 10,000 civilians died, 300,000 people were expelled and became refugees due to the intervention of Russia; the War in Tskhinvali; the Civil war in the center of Tbilisi, Russian soldiers dispersed the participants of the peaceful protest and shoved the girls and boys like pearls, 21 young people died, thousands were poisoned with gas. Then power cutting, powerlessness, unbearable situation...

At that time, the European Union did not exist and it was called the European Community. It was called the European Union since 1993. At that time, there was little information about the European Union, and there were no such communication technologies, as the Internet. However, it was during this period that Georgia's relationship with the European Union began. At that time, European support was limited to humanitarian aid: food, clothing, medicines...

Discussion

Today, the support of the European Union means carrying out democratic and economic reforms, bringing them closer to the standards of the European Union. During this 30-year relationship, the European Union implemented projects worth more than 2.5 billion euros in Georgia... During the Covid pandemic, it provided financial assistance of up to 300 million euros; Education support (Erasmus+), financing of 6,000 students in European universities, support for the mobility of Georgian scientists; Visa-free travel in the Schengen area, which can be enjoyed by all citizens, regardless of their status.

The signing of the association agreement with the European Union is an important success for Georgia, Georgian companies can sell their products in the European Union at a non-tariff barrier. Therefore, the European Union is the most important trade partner for

Georgia. On June 23, 2022, the European Council granted Georgia the status of a potential candidate. This decision is for Georgia, Moldova, and Ukraine. We are increasingly showing the intended goal.

The President of the European Commission, Ursula von der Leyen, also spoke about the historical significance of the decision of June 23, when she explained, from the rostrum of the European Parliament, in her annual report on the future of Europe, that "you [the peoples of Georgia, Moldova, Ukraine and the Western Balkans] are part of our family, your future is the European Union, The European Union is incomplete without you." On this level European Union has determined the main directions for Georgia (there are 12 creations), which should be necessary along with the fulfillment of several obligations (Copenhagen criteria) and the legislation of the European Union. The EU Self-Assessment Questionnaire consists of 2 main parts: political and economic criteria.

The economic criteria include two major chapters: 1. The level of development of a functional market economy; 2. Ability to deal with market competition within the EU.

I reckon Georgia has successfully managed to meet the economic criteria. Impressive progress has been made in terms of economic development and improvement of the business environment. According to the data of the National Statistics Service of Georgia, in 2022 the share of direct foreign investments in GDP will reach 8.3%. (FDI= 2 billion USD, GDP 24 billion USD). This index significantly exceeds the index of previous years. According to the Economic Freedom Index of the Heritage Foundation, which evaluates the state of countries on a scale of 0-100 points, where a score of 100 corresponds to the highest level of economic freedom, the overall economic freedom score of

Georgia is 68.7; 35th place in the world ranking. Heritage Foundation publishes the following indicators of the economic freedom of Georgia in 2022:¹

Business freedom 69,8	Labor market freedom – 62,1
Monetary freedom- 72,0	Governmental interference in economics – 73,8
Fiscal freedom - 87,2	Trade freedom – 86.0
Investment freedom – 80.0	Finance freedom 80.0.

It is also mentioned that Georgia takes 21th place among 44 European countries and its overall score is much higher than the world and regional average. Georgia is considered a "moderately free" economy and performs quite well in some key policy areas. Significant reforms have been implemented to increase the effectiveness of regulation and open market policies have been maintained along with low tax rates. The economy has shown a high level of resilience. Access to financing in the banking sector has improved.²

According to the index of economic freedom, the countries are divided into free, mostly free, moderately free, mostly not free, repressed countries:³

Free countries whose index ranges from 100 to 80 include four countries: Singapore - 83.9; Switzerland 83.8; Ireland 82.0, Taiwan 80.7.

Mostly free countries (with an index range of 80-70). It includes 22 countries. Among them are: New Zealand -78.9; Estonia – 78.6; Luxembourg -78.4; Netherlands -78.0; Denmark – 77.6; Sweden - 77.5; South Korea - 73.7, etc.

Moderate free countries (70-60). It includes 55 countries Among them are Latvia, Poland, Slovakia, Bulgaria, Albania, Kazakhstan, Turkey, Azerbaijan, Slovenia, and Serbia, Georgia is in 35th place with a score of 68.7.

Mostly not free countries include 32 countries: (59,9-50): Moldova (58,5); Ghana (58,0); Angola India (52,9); Russia (53,8); Belarus 51,0, etc.

Trade liberalization is the most important step towards the free participation of the country in the international division of labor. Georgia's foreign policy is focused on the diversification of trade relations. In terms of its implementation in the field of trade, the country's membership in the World Trade Organization (WTO), which is a powerful institution that creates a trade system based on the principles of mutual agreement and mutual benefit, is important. 95% of world trade takes place within it. The WTO Agreement is a framework that determines the nature of the trade policies of countries. Georgia is an active participant in the multilateral trade system. Our country's foreign trade and foreign investment have increased significantly since the pandemic. Foreign trade is more than 19 billion USD according to preliminary data for 2022. Exports are 5 billion 600 million US dollars, and imports

are 13 billion 600 million US dollars. Exports have increased even without re-exports and amount to 3 billion 700 million.⁴

In recent years, Georgian products have been exported to China, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Turkey, Armenia, etc. in the largest amount from EU countries. As for the rest of the countries, Georgia's export volume was relatively high in Canada, Great Britain, and the United Arab Emirates.

The volume of direct foreign investments is also an important indicator of the country's integration with the global economy. The highest share of foreign direct investment comes from manufacturing, which contributes to the development of the economy, followed by trade, transport, and information technology.

Georgia can play the role of a transit country, which attracts the attention of the international community. Its geopolitical and geo-economic position is a subject of international interest.

For a country with such a small economy as Georgia, gaining an international function, and full membership of the European Union, is necessary in the difficult process of state building, not only from an economic point of view but also from a political viewpoint. In the long term, with the expansion of the transport corridor, more foreign investment will be attracted. Accordingly, such fields as telecommunications, energy, hotels, industrial and agricultural production, and other service fields will be developed.

Georgia's attractiveness to investors focused on market size is not so high. Nevertheless, the interest of foreign companies in Georgia is growing, because the country is a kind of bridge that connects the most important regions of the world with its location. These are Europe (population of 740 million), Black Sea basin countries (population of 243 million), Turkey (population of 85 million), and the Caucasus region (25 million). By investing in Georgia, foreign companies can serve the markets of the region and strengthen their positions.

According to the "Doing Business 2019" report of the World Bank and the International Finance Corporation, **Georgia ranks 7th among 190 countries** according to the index of favorable conditions for doing business. and **Moldova takes 48th place**. All economies are compared as of May 2020. The following countries are in the first ten with this indicator: New Zealand, Singapore, Hong Kong, Denmark, Korea, USA, Georgia, Great Britain, Norway, and Sweden. Also, **Georgia ranked second** among the fastest reforming countries in terms of improved business environment, and **Moldova ranked 13th**.

Conclusion

Finally, in conclusion, it should be said that the level of competitiveness of Georgia, technological development, as well as the quality of the national business environment will be significantly improved by deepening the cooperation with the European Union. I have nothing against Moldova, but Georgia is ahead of

¹ <http://www.heritage.org/index/country/georgia>

² <https://www.heritage.org/index/country/georgia>

³ <http://www.heritage.org/index/ranking>

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<https://www.geostat.ge/ka/modules/categories/765/sakonlitsagareo-vachroba>

Moldova in important economic parameters. At the same time, Moldova is still within the CIS. Georgia officially left the CIS on August 18, 2009. And if only Ukraine and Moldova are granted candidate status, it will be an injustice to Georgia, to the Georgian society, which is so persistently trying to unite with the European Union.

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